

The impact of social media marketing (SMM) on repurchase intention with e-Wom and brand image as mediation (study on consumers of Lemonilo instant noodles in Malang city)

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Abstract

This study aims to examine the influence of Social Media Marketing (SMM) on repurchase intention of Lemonilo Instant Noodle products, mediated by Electronic Word of Mouth (E-WOM) and brand image. The research method employed is quantitative, collecting data through questionnaires distributed to Lemonilo Instant Noodle consumers, with a sample size of 202 respondents meeting the sampling criteria. Data were analyzed statistically using Smart PLS. The results indicate that SMM significantly affects repurchase intention, E-WOM, and brand image. Furthermore, E-WOM and brand image have a significant impact on repurchase intention. Moreover, E-WOM and brand image mediate the relationship between SMM and repurchase intention. Consumers engaged in E-WOM feel more confident and satisfied with the product, while a strong brand image makes consumers more tolerant of product shortcomings. This study suggests that Lemonilo Instant Noodles continue to enhance SMM strategies, strengthen environmental-friendly initiatives, and encourage consumer participation in E-WOM to build sustainable loyalty. Thus, effective marketing strategies can foster deeper connections with consumers, bolster brand image, and increase repurchase intention.

Keywords: Brand Image; Electronic Word of Mouth; Repurchase Intention; Social Media Marketing.

1. Introduction

Social Media Marketing (SMM) has a huge impact on resources and services to make them available to remote customers. (Anwar & Zhiwei, 2020). SMM enables two-way interaction to engage with current and potential customers. (Jalil et al., 2021). This is an important approach for businesses to build product and brand relationships with customers, so marketers utilize SMM to conduct Integrated marketing communications (IMC), such as Instagram, facebook, whatsapp and the like to convey clear and consistent messages about the organization and its products. (Luxton et al., 2015).

Through SMM, companies can disseminate high-quality content and information to consumers. These contents can be in the form of articles, videos, infographics, and others that not only promote products or services but are able to reach a wider range of customers. (Cooley & Parks-Yancy, 2019).

The advantages of SMM are widely adopted by companies including Lemonilo in carrying out their marketing activities. Lemonilo is a brand of food and health products, especially instant noodles, that focuses on organic food and healthy lifestyle. Lemonilo's first marketing and sales strategy is to use social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter. The use of social media is to promote their products, interact with customers, and build a community of users who support each other, as well as build a brand image. Through SMM, Lemonilo's brand image is closely associated with health and hygiene values. Their products are often identified with the labels "healthy" and "natural," which can create a positive image among consumers who care about a healthy lifestyle. In addition, Lemonilo's use of SMM to

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increase brand awareness, introduce new products, and inform about offers and discounts is expected to reach a wider audience, build closer relationships with customers, and promote their healthy lifestyle.

The issues faced by Lemonilo in maintaining consistency in posting content on social media platforms can have a huge impact on Electronic Word-of-Mouth (e-WOM) or online brand talk. Lack of engaging content can reduce interaction from users on social media platforms, which can affect e-WOM. Lack of user participation can mean a lack of positive talk or recommendations among the online community. Coupled with complaints or issues surfacing on social media platforms, slow or ineffective handling can be detrimental to a brand's reputation. Poorly addressed complaints can have a negative impact on e-WOM, as users are likely to talk about their negative experiences. This can have an impact on the company's sales performance. Lemonilo instant noodle sales performance data can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Comparison of Sales Performance of Lemonilo, Indomie and Sedap Brand Instant Noodles

The graph in Figure 1 shows that the sales trend of Indomie and Sedap Instant Noodles from January to August 2022 tends to experience a significant increase. Meanwhile, the Lemonilo brand of Instant Noodles from February tends to decrease until August, namely from Rp765.3 million to Rp176.1 million or a decrease of 76.99%. This data indicates that the repurchase intention of customers is decreasing.

Repurchase intention is defined as a customer's decision to repeat a purchase from a particular brand after using a product for the first time. (Shabankareh et al., 2022). It also refers to the customer's opinion about the current situation that allows them to buy the same product in the future. (Shabankareh et al., 2023).. Repurchase intention shows the attitude of customer loyalty (Chiu et al., 2009). Therefore, in the midst of this increasingly fierce business competition, industries compete to acquire new customers and retain existing customers in order to survive and develop.

Business owners now see customer switching behavior as a complex phenomenon, so they must determine what makes them consider repurchasing goods that have been lost. (Ismail, 2022). Customers' perceptions can see changes in inducements and obstacles simultaneously and if there are no barriers, this can lead to incorrect perceptions of customer behavior, leading to incorrect conclusions and ineffective management actions. (Chuah et al., 2017). Through SMM provides an opportunity for companies to interact directly and be able to maintain relationships with their customers. By responding positively and quickly to customer comments, questions or feedback, companies can build closer relationships and strengthen bonds with customers and make it possible to repurchase from the company.

Previous findings show that SMM has a significant effect on repurchase intention on halal domestic products. (Wangpo & Wangmo, 2022; Jalil et al., 2021). Nonetheless, little attention has been paid to evaluating repurchase intention on Lemonilo Instant Noodle products with reference to SMM which is a key strategic factor with high managerial impact. Besides, there are research gaps, such as those conducted by Mainolfi et al. (2022); Dulek & Aydin (2020) that there is no significant influence between SMM and repurchase intentions. The results show that there is still a research gap between the influence of SMM and repurchase intentions, so it needs to be followed up by involving mediating variables as a link between the two. The mediating variables used are Electronic Worth of Mouth (E-WOM) and brand image.

E-WOM is an informal internet-based communication tool that allows consumers to evaluate the specific functions of goods and services before using them. (Mainolfi et al., 2022).. Through SMM, information about products and companies is spread through communication platforms such as social networks, intense information exchange between users is preferred. This encourages customers to conduct E-WOM through various channels, such as virtual communities, websites, sites that provide product reviews, and social media. (Styvén et al., 2020), so that it can have an impact on repurchase intentions. Previous findings by Dulek & Aydin (2020) found that E-WOM is able to mediate the influence between SMM and repurchase intentions. However, contrary to the findings of Jalil et al. (2021) who found that E-WOM could not mediate the influence between the two.

Brand image is a mental image of consumers (Dobni & Zinkhan, 1990). Kotler & Keller (2016) claims that brand image is a set of beliefs, ideas, and impressions customers have of a brand; therefore customers' actions and attitudes towards a brand are likely to depend on brand image. Through SMM, Lemonilo can build and strengthen a positive brand image in the eyes of customers. Interesting content, useful information, satisfied customer testimonials, and positive interactions with customers can form positive perceptions of the brand. This positive perception can increase customers' intention to repurchase the company's products or services. (Huang et al., 2019). Previous findings show that Fajar & Wardi (2022); Wangpo & Wangmo (2022) showed that brand image mediates the influence between SMM and repurchase intention. However, contrary to the findings Fahmi et al. (2019) that brand image does not significantly mediate between the effects of the two variables.

Referring to the previous description, the repurchase intention has decreased, which is suspected to be due to the SMM that is applied less optimally. In addition, previous research found a research gap, so the authors are interested in evaluating the effect of SMM on repurchase intentions on Lemonilo Instant Noodle products mediated by E-WOM and brand image. Through this research, it is hoped that deep insights into the dynamics of interactions between SMM, E-WOM, brand image, and consumer repurchase intentions in the instant noodle sector can be found, providing a basis for the development of more sophisticated and effective marketing strategies. Lemonilo and similar companies can formulate a more targeted approach in building strong relationships with consumers through social media and enhance their competitiveness in an increasingly digitally connected market.

Figure 2 Thinking Framework Model

1.1 Methods

This type of research is quantitative research. Quantitative research involves the use of scientific and statistical approaches to measure variables, identify causal relationships, and make generalizations from samples to larger populations. (Creswell, 2014). The population of this study is all consumers of Lemonilo Instant Noodles in Malang city. However, researchers conducted research sampling. Research sampling uses purposive sampling method or is based on certain criteria. The sample criteria in this study include respondents who are at least 18 years old who have bought

and consumed Lemonilo Instant Noodles at least in the last 3 months; and follow Lemonilo's social media, either Instagram, Facebook, Twitter, and the like.

The data in this study are primary data. According to Creswell (2014) states that primary data is data obtained directly by researchers to analyze a specific problem. In this study, the primary data collection method used a survey through the distribution of questionnaires. The distribution of questionnaires was carried out online via google form. In addition, the author asked the help of Lemonilo's social media managers to distribute it through their social media in order to obtain respondents who met the research criteria.

This test was tested through Smart PLS with three stages of testing: research instrument test, inner model and hypothesis testing. The research instrument test or outer model test is used to evaluate the feasibility of the instrument with three testing methods, namely: convergent validity, composite reliability, and discriminant validity. Inner model test to evaluate the feasibility of the structural model with three methods, namely: R Square, Q Square, and Goodness of Fit (GoF). Hypothesis testing is used to analyze the influence between the variables studied and prove the proposed hypotheses, namely H1-H5. This test is carried out multivariately through Smart PLS with the criteria that the P-Value value ≤ 0.05 , the research hypothesis is accepted. (Hair et al., 2021).

This study uses independent, dependent, and mediating variables. Independent variables are the types of variables that can affect other variables or are referred to as independent variables. The dependent variable is a type of variable that can be influenced by other variables or is called the dependent variable. Meanwhile, the mediating variable is a connecting variable between the independent variable and the dependent variable. In this study, SMM is an independent variable; repurchase intention is a type of dependent variable; while E-WOM and brand image are mediating variables. The operational definitions of the variables are as follows.

Table 1 Operational Definition and Measurement of Research Variables

Vari ables	Operational Definition	Item	Indicator	Statement	Source
Repu rchas e Inten tion	The degree to which customers are willing and likely to purchase Lemonilo Instant Noodle products again in the future, based on positive evaluations of previous experiences with the product, preferences for product attributes	PI1	Intention to keep using the product	I will continue to consume Lemonilo Instant Noodles	Ismail (2022)
		PI2	Prioritization of future product use	I prioritize consuming Lemonilo Instant Noodles in the future	
		PI3	Not easily switch to other brands	If there are shortcomings in Lemonilo Instant Noodles, I do not immediately switch brands.	
Socia l Medi a Mark eting (SM M)	A strategy that involves the use of social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and others to promote Lemonilo Instant Noodle products	SM1	Posting frequency	Environmentally friendly activities for Lemonilo Instant Noodles are often carried out seen through social media	Suttikun & Mahasuweerachai (2023)
		SM2	Satisfaction and expectations	The level of social media advertising about environmentally friendly activities for Lemonilo Instant Noodles matches my expectations.	
		SM3	Visual appeal	Social media advertisements about environmentally friendly activities for Lemonilo Instant Noodles are very interesting	

		SM4	Performance compared to competitors	Social media advertising on eco-friendly activities for Lemonilo Instant Noodles works well compared to other Instant Noodles	
		SM5	Extensive	Lemonilo Instant Noodles offers extensive advertisements on eco-friendly activities through social media	
		SM6	Easy to remember	Lemonilo Instant Noodles advertised on social media by offering an easy-to-remember eco-friendly activity	
E-WOM	The process where Lemonilo Instant Noodle customers share experiences, reviews, and product recommendations through online platforms such as review sites, social media (such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram), discussion groups, online forums, or instant messaging applications.	EW1	Comment activity	I actively comment on Lemonilo Instant Noodle products	Pang & Wang (2023)
		EW2	Recommendation to friends	I would like to recommend Lemonilo Instant Noodle products to my friends	
		EW3	Retweet activity	I actively retweet Lemonilo Instant Noodle products to my friendship circle accounts	
Brand Image	Consumer perceptions of the Lemonilo Instant Noodle brand based on attributes such as the image of the maker, user and product.	BI1	Maker image	Lemonilo Instant Noodles are popular	Aaker (1991)
		BI2	User Image	Lemonilo Instant Noodle users are confident when consuming the brand	
		BI3	Product image	Lemonilo Instant Noodle Brand is instant noodles made from natural ingredients.	

2. Results and discussion

2.1 Respondent Description

This research data was obtained through the distribution of questionnaires. The questionnaire was distributed via google form to respondents who live in Malang City. The number of respondents in this study who met the sample criteria totaled 202 respondents. The following is a description of respondents based on gender, age, education, and occupation. Table 2 shows that most respondents were female (125 respondents; 61.9%) compared to male (77 respondents; 38.1%). These results indicate that women tend to be more concerned about healthy food for themselves and their families especially on Lemonilo instant noodle products compared to men. Most respondents were aged 18 years to 30 years (130 respondents; 64.0%), followed by 31 years to 45 years (27 respondents; 13.4%), aged > 60 years (23 respondents; 11.4%) and the least were aged 46 years to 60 years (22 respondents; 10.9%). These results show that young people tend to be more concerned and aware of the nutritional and health aspects of the food they consume compared to older people, and Lemonilo is known as a healthy instant noodle product for consumption.

Table 2 shows that most respondents had a Bachelor's/Postgraduate education (96 respondents; 47.5%), followed by a high school/vocational school education (63 respondents; 31.2%), a junior high school education (29 respondents; 14.4%), and the least had an elementary school education and were not in school or did not graduate from elementary

school (7 respondents; 3.5%). These results indicate that respondents with higher levels of education are more concerned with the quality of the food they consume, and tend to choose healthier foods such as Lemonilo instant noodles. Most respondents work as students (89 respondents; 43.8%), followed by those with high school/vocational school education (73 respondents; 36.1%), followed by the self-employed (61 respondents; 30.2%), private employees (40 respondents; 19.8%), civil servants (16 respondents; 7.9%), and the least as state-owned employees (12 respondents; 5.9%). These results show that students are more concerned with the quality of the food they consume, and tend to choose healthier foods such as Lemonilo instant noodles.

Table 2 Respondent Description

Characteristics	Category	Frequency	%
Gender	Male	77	38.1
	Female	125	61.9
Age	18-30 years old	130	64.4
	31-45 years old	27	13.4
	46-60 years old	22	10.9
	>60 years	23	11.4
Education	Not in School / Graduated	7	3.5
	Elementary School Equivalent	7	3.5
	Junior High School	29	14.4
	SMA/SMK Equivalent	63	31.2
	Undergraduate/Postgraduate	96	47.5
Jobs	Student/MHS	73	36.1
	PNS	16	7.9
	SOE Employee	12	5.9
	Private Employee	40	19.8
	Self-employed	61	30.2
Total		202	100%

2.2 Outer Model Evaluation

Table 3 Outer Model Test Results

Variables	Item	Loading Factor	Cronbach Alpha	ρc	AVE	Results
Repurchase Intention	PI1	0.756	0.720	0.839	0.635	Valid and Reliable
	PI2	0.775				
	PI3	0.856				
Social Media Marketing (SMM)	SM1	0.647	0.831	0.877	0.546	Valid and Reliable
	SM2	0.704				
	SM3	0.616				
	SM4	0.831				
	SM5	0.798				
	SM6	0.810				

E-WOM	EW1	0.877	0.809	0.887	0.724	Valid and Reliable
	EW2	0.834				
	EW3	0.841				
Brand Image	BI1	0.757	0.755	0.859	0.670	Valid and Reliable
	BI2	0.863				
	BI3	0.832				

The outer model test is carried out to assess the feasibility of the instrument using three approaches, namely: convergent validity, composite reliability, and discriminant validity. The results of the convergent validity evaluation in Table 3 show that the loading factor value is > 0.50 . This means that it can be concluded that the research data meets the convergent validity criteria. The composite reliability evaluation results have a Cronbach Alpha value > 0.60 and a ρ_c value > 0.70 . Thus it can be concluded that the research data meets the composite reliability criteria. The results of the discriminant validity evaluation show that it has an AVE value > 0.50 . This means that the research results show that the data studied meet the discriminant validity criteria. From the three outer model evaluation results, it can be concluded that the data meets the instrument quality, so it is feasible to test the inner model.

2.3 Inner Model Evaluation

Inner model testing is conducted to assess the feasibility of the structural model and determine whether the research model fits the model being tested. There are three approaches used: R Square (R^2), Q Square (Q^2), and Goodness of Fit (GoF). The research results in Table 4 show that brand image has an R^2 value of 0.193 which is classified as weak, a Q^2 value of 0.121 which is moderate, and a GoF value of 0.325 which is also moderate. This indicates that the brand image model has sufficient predictability, but not very strong. E-WOM showed better results with an R^2 of 0.555 (moderate), Q^2 of 0.394 (strong), and GoF of 0.551 (strong). This indicates that the E-WOM model has a fairly strong and reliable predictability. Meanwhile, repurchase intention has an R^2 of 0.564 (moderate), Q^2 of 0.331 (moderate), and GoF of 0.604 (strong). These results indicate that the repurchase intention model has good predictability and is suitable for use. The overall research results show that E-WOM and repurchase intentions show higher model strength than brand image. The data shows that the research model has varying degrees of feasibility with higher strength in E-WOM and repurchase intentions.

Table 4 Inner Model Test Results

Model	R2	Q2	GoF
Brand Image	0.193 (weak)	0.121 (moderate)	0.325 (moderate)
E-WOM	0.555 (moderate)	0.394 (strong)	0.551 (strong)
Repurchase Intention	0.564 (moderate)	0.331 (moderate)	0.604 (strong)

2.4 Hypothesis Test Results

The next step is to conduct hypothesis testing to test the influence between variables. This test aims to determine whether there is a significant relationship between the variables studied. The criterion used is a P-value ≤ 0.05 , which indicates an influence between variables and the hypothesis can be accepted. The hypothesis test results in Table 5 show that SMM has a significant influence on repurchase intention with β of 0.483, T and P-Value of 0.000, which means H1 is accepted. These results indicate that SMM significantly has a positive effect on repurchase intentions. Furthermore, SMM has a significant effect on E-WOM with β of 0.745 and a P-Value of 0.000, which can confirm that H2 is accepted. These results indicate that SMM has a significant positive effect on E-WOM. In addition, SMM has a significant effect on brand image with β of 0.440 and P-Value of 0.000, which means H3 is accepted, indicating that SMM has a significant positive effect on brand image.

Table 5 Hypothesis Test Results

	β	T Stat	P Values	Results
SMM-> Repurchase Intention	0.483	5.060	0.000**	H1 accepted
SMM->E-WOM	0.745	20.469	0.000**	H2 accepted
SMM->Brand Image	0.440	5.670	0.000**	H3 accepted
E-WOM -> Repurchase Intention	0.208	2.531	0.012*	H4 accepted
Brand Image -> Repurchase Intention	0.183	3.171	0.002**	H5 accepted
SMM->E-WOM -> Repurchase Intention	0.155	2.531	0.012*	H6 accepted
SMM->Brand Image -> Repurchase Intention	0.081	2.549	0.011*	H7 accepted

Notes: ** significant at α 0.01 (1%); * significant at α 0.05 (5%).

The results of hypothesis testing show that E-WOM has a significant positive effect on repurchase intentions with β of 0.208 and a P-Value of 0.012, so H4 is accepted. In addition, brand image has a significant positive effect on repurchase intentions with a β of 0.183 P-Value of 0.002. Thus, H5 is accepted. The indirect effect can be seen from the hypothesis test results. SMM has a significant effect on repurchase intention through E-WOM with β of 0.155 and a P-Value of 0.012, so H6 is accepted. Furthermore, SMM has a significant influence on repurchase intention through brand image with β of 0.081 and a P-Value of 0.011, so H7 is accepted.

3. Discussion

3.1 The Effect of SMM on Repurchase Intention

The results showed that SMM has a significant positive effect on repurchase intentions on Lemonilo Instant Noodle products, so H1 is accepted. The research shows that SMM activities focused on Lemonilo Instant Noodles' environmentally friendly activities play an important role in shaping consumers' repurchase intentions. Through consumers' frequent viewing of Lemonilo's green activities on social media, they become more aware of the brand's commitment to the environment and are encouraged to keep choosing the product in the future. The level of social media advertising that matches consumers' expectations and desires strengthens their emotional connection with the brand, making them feel heard and valued. (Kotler & Keller, 2016). In addition, the highly engaging advertisements about Lemonilo Instant Noodles' eco-friendly activities create a positive and deep impression in consumers' minds, encouraging them to reconsider purchasing the product. Lemonilo ads being perceived as better and more effective than other brands' ads, consumers tend to feel more confident and satisfied with their choice, increasing their intention to remain loyal to the brand.

Offering extensive and memorable advertisements about its eco-friendly activities through social media, Lemonilo managed to build strong awareness and ongoing knowledge among consumers about their commitment to social and environmental responsibility. As a result, consumers feel emotionally connected to the brand and feel they have a role in supporting Lemonilo's mission and values, which in turn increases their propensity to make repeat purchases. Thus, it can be concluded that SMM influences repurchase intentions on Lemonilo Instant Noodle products through consistent disclosure of environmental commitments, recognition of consumer preferences and expectations, creation of engaging and effective advertisements, and ongoing building of awareness and knowledge about the brand. These results are supported by previous research by Ramadhania et al. (2023)Wangpo & Wangmo (2022) that SMM can increase consumer intention in repurchasing a product.

3.2 The Effect of SMM on E-WOM

The results showed that SMM has a significant positive effect on E-WOM on Lemonilo Instant Noodle products, so H2 is accepted. This study highlights that the SMM strategies carried out by Lemonilo Instant Noodles, especially related to environmentally friendly activities, significantly affect the level of E-WOM generated by consumers. Through frequent viewing of Lemonilo's green activities on social media, consumers felt emotionally engaged and encouraged to be part of the online conversation about the brand. When advertisements about green activities match consumers' expectations and desires, it gives the impression that the Lemonilo brand understands and meets their needs. This encourages consumers to actively comment on Lemonilo products, as they feel heard and valued by the brand. In addition, the highly engaging advertisements about Lemonilo's eco-friendly activities created a high buzz and interest among consumers,

encouraging them to actively recommend the products to their friends. As such, consumers feel proud and excited to share their positive experiences with others, which is reflected in activities such as retweeting Lemonilo products to their circle of friends.

When Lemonilo offers extensive and memorable advertisements about its eco-friendly activities through social media, this not only increases consumers' awareness of the brand, but also reinforces their positive impression of it. As a result, consumers are more likely to engage in positive E-WOM, whether through comments, recommendations, or retweets. The results of this study are in line with the findings by Ismail (2022); Mainolfi et al. (2022) that E-WOM can be enhanced through effective SMM.

3.3 The Effect of SMM on Brand Image

The results showed that SMM has a significant positive effect on brand image of Lemonilo Instant Noodle products, so H3 is accepted. This study shows that the SMM strategy carried out by Lemonilo Instant Noodles, especially related to environmentally friendly activities, has a significant impact on the brand's image. Through consumers' frequent viewing of Lemonilo's eco-friendly activities on social media, they increasingly believe that the brand is actively contributing to environmental sustainability. This creates a positive impression that Lemonilo Instant Noodles is a brand that cares about the environment, which directly increases the brand's popularity. When advertisements about green activities match consumers' expectations and desires, it strengthens their belief in the authenticity and integrity of the brand. In addition, attractive and effective advertisements about Lemonilo's green activities make the brand memorable to consumers. This gives the impression that Lemonilo Instant Noodles is a unique brand and stands out among other brands, which in turn increases consumers' trust in the brand.

Along with popularity and consumer trust, the brand image of Lemonilo Instant Noodles has become stronger and more positive. Consumers feel proud and confident when consuming Lemonilo products because they feel connected to the brand values that reflect concern for the environment and the use of natural ingredients in their products. Thus, it can be concluded that SMM positively influences the brand image of Lemonilo Instant Noodles through creating a positive impression of environmental stewardship, recognizing consumer preferences, and building strong awareness of the brand in the minds of consumers. The results of this study are in line with the findings by Ramadhania et al. (2023); Wangpo & Wangmo (2022); Fajar & Wardi (2022) that SMM can significantly improve brand image.

3.4 The Effect of E-WOM on Repurchase Intention

The results showed that E-WOM has a significant positive effect on the repurchase intention of Lemonilo Instant Noodle products, so H4 is accepted. Consumers who actively comment on Lemonilo products indicate that they have positive experiences and high satisfaction with the product. Consumers feel satisfied and emotionally involved with the brand. Consumers are likely to continue consuming the product in the future. In addition, consumers' willingness to recommend Lemonilo products to their friends reflects their high level of trust and confidence in the quality of the products. Recommendations from trusted people have a major impact in strengthening repurchase decisions, as potential consumers tend to trust reviews and recommendations from friends and family more than regular advertisements. (Dong et al., 2024).

The activity of retweeting Lemonilo products to their circle of friends shows that consumers have a positive and strong relationship with the brand. When consumers share their positive experiences publicly on social media, this not only strengthens their own loyalty, but also influences others to try and stick with Lemonilo products. Thus, high E-WOM activities, such as commenting on, recommending, and retweeting Lemonilo products, play an important role in driving repurchase intentions. These results are in line with the findings by Ismail (2022); Mainolfi et al. (2022); Jalil et al. (2021) that E-WOM can encourage a person's intention to make a repurchase.

3.5 The Effect of Brand Image on Repurchase Intention

This study shows that a strong and positive brand image has a significant influence on consumer repurchase intentions for Lemonilo Instant Noodle products, so H5 is accepted. When Lemonilo Instant Noodles are considered popular, this indicates that the product has a good reputation and is widely recognized by consumers. This popularity gives consumers confidence that they are making the right choice by consuming a product that is in high demand. In addition, Lemonilo Instant Noodle users feel confident when consuming the brand. This confidence arises from the belief that they consume quality products and are recognized by many people.

Furthermore, Lemonilo Instant Noodles' image as instant noodles made from natural ingredients provides important added value to consumers who are concerned about health and the environment. Consumers who believe that the

product is made from natural ingredients are more likely to remain loyal to the brand, as they feel confident that the product is good for their health and the environment. This is very important in maintaining repurchase intentions, as consumers are more likely to keep consuming products that they perceive to be safe and of high quality. (Jalilvand & Samiei, 2012).. The results of this study are in line with the findings by Wangpo & Wangmo (2022); Fajar & Wardi (2022) that there is a significant influence between brand image on repurchase intentions.

3.6 The Effect of SMM on Repurchase Intention Mediated by E-WOM

This study reveals that an effective SMM strategy can influence consumers' repurchase intention towards Lemonilo Instant Noodle products by strengthening E-WOM, so H6 is accepted. When Lemonilo's eco-friendly activities are frequently featured on social media, consumers become more aware of the brand's commitment to environmental issues, which increases their interest and support for the product. The level of social media advertising that matches consumers' expectations makes them feel valued and understood by the brand, which encourages them to actively share their positive experiences. Engaging advertisements about Lemonilo's eco-friendly activities increased consumer engagement and created a desire to recommend the product to their friends. This can be seen from the statements of consumers who actively commented on, recommended, and retweeted Lemonilo products, indicating that they had positive experiences that they wanted to share with their circle of friends.

According to Ismail (2022) this strong E-WOM plays an important role in influencing repurchase intentions. When consumers actively participate in E-WOM, they not only share positive reviews and recommendations, but also reinforce their own purchasing decisions. Positive experiences shared by others in their social network reinforce their belief that Lemonilo products are a good choice, increasing their confidence to continue consuming the products in the future. Consumers who feel social support and validation from their community are more likely to remain loyal to Lemonilo products despite any drawbacks they may encounter.

Thus, it can be concluded that effective SMM influences repurchase intentions through increased E-WOM. Consumers who engage in Lemonilo's eco-friendly activities on social media and feel that the advertisement meets their expectations are more likely to actively comment, recommend, and retweet the product. These E-WOM activities reinforce their intention to continue consuming Lemonilo Instant Noodles, prioritize the product in the future, and not immediately switch brands despite the drawbacks. This suggests that SMM that successfully increases E-WOM can create stronger and more sustainable consumer loyalty. These results are supported by previous research that E-WOM is able to mediate the influence between SMM on repurchase intentions (Dulek & Aydin, 2020).

3.7 The Effect of SMM on Repurchase Intention Mediated by Brand Image

This study found that the SMM strategy implemented by Lemonilo Instant Noodles has a significant influence on consumer repurchase intentions through improving brand image, so H7 is accepted. SMM that emphasizes environmentally friendly activities and is often displayed on social media has succeeded in building a positive image for Lemonilo. Consumers who often see these environmentally friendly activities, they increasingly believe that Lemonilo Instant Noodles is a brand that cares about the environment, which increases the brand's popularity. Social media ads that are engaging and in line with consumers' expectations strengthen their belief in the authenticity and quality of the product (Zarei et al., 2011). (Zarei et al., 2022).. For example, ads that show that Lemonilo Instant Noodles are made from natural ingredients attract health-conscious consumers, reinforcing the brand image as a healthy and natural choice.

A strong brand image, as seen from the statement that Lemonilo Instant Noodles are popular and make users feel confident when consuming them, strongly influences repurchase intentions. Consumers who feel proud and confident in their choice tend to remain loyal to the product. Consumers feel that choosing Lemonilo is the right decision and want to continue consuming this product in the future. Even if there are flaws in the product, a positive brand image makes consumers more tolerant and does not immediately switch to another brand.

Thus, it can be concluded that effective SMM improves brand image, which in turn affects consumers' repurchase intentions. Consumers who see advertisements about Lemonilo's eco-friendly activities and feel that the brand is popular, natural, and trustworthy are more likely to keep consuming the product. They prioritize Lemonilo in the future and do not immediately switch brands despite the drawbacks. This suggests that SMM that successfully builds and strengthens brand image can create stronger and more sustainable consumer loyalty to Lemonilo Instant Noodles. These results are in line with the findings by Fajar & Wardi (2022); Wangpo & Wangmo (2022) that brand image is able to mediate the influence between SMM on repurchase intentions.

4. Conclusion

Based on the research, Social Media Marketing (SMM) is proven to have a significant positive influence on repurchase intentions, Electronic Word of Mouth (E-WOM), and brand image of Lemonilo instant noodle products. E-WOM and brand image also have a positive influence on repurchase intentions. In addition, E-WOM and brand image mediate the influence between SMM and repurchase intention, suggesting that an effective SMM strategy can strengthen consumer loyalty through increased E-WOM and positive brand image. Therefore, Lemonilo Instant Noodles is advised to increase the intensity and quality of SMM, especially focusing on environmentally friendly activities to build a strong emotional connection with consumers. Campaigns that encourage consumers to share their experiences on social media and use various platforms to reach a wider audience can increase E-WOM and SMM effectiveness. In addition, actively monitoring consumer reviews and responding quickly to them can increase consumer loyalty. Future research is recommended to add moderating variables such as gender roles to deepen the understanding of the influence of SMM on repurchase intentions.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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